

Investigation of Some Indigenous Medicinal Plants Regularly Used in Cooking Daily Curries by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (Aas) Method

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Abstract

Human requires a number of mineral in order to maintain good health. Herbal foods can contribute significantly to human nutrition and health, because they contain almost all essential human nutrients. In this paper, analysis of elemental concentrations with respect to some indigenous medicinal plants (Pudina, Pinsane, Nannan, Pyinntawthein) regularly used in cooking daily curries by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy Method. From this results, it was found that these medicinal plants are rich in some essential minerals for human health.

Keywords – Medicinal plants, minerals, toxic elements, AAS

Introduction

Traditional diet is initially vegetarian and consists of various cereals and vegetables along with spices, used in the preparation of daily curries. Traditional diets has long been considered as the major source of human exposure to trace elements and consequently the levels in basic foodstuff, but medicinal uptakes are more interested from the toxicological and nutritional points of view.

Human requires a number of minerals in order to maintain good health. Essential minerals to human nutrition are accumulated in different parts of plants as it accumulates essential minerals for growth from the environment. Study of elements with respect to indigenous medicinal plants reveals that major and trace elements have significant roles in combating a variety of human ailments and disease. In this work, among four samples of medicinal plants, Pudina (Keerai spinach) is known as calm stomach cramps and helps beat acidity and flatulence. The leaves of Pudina are used fresh, dried or frozen and can be preserved in salt, sugar or oil. Pudina leaves can be used in both raw and cooked applications such as stir-frying, steaming, sautéing and boiling. They can be added to salads and are commonly used in soups, stir-fries, rice dishes, dales and curries. Pudina has been used in traditional medicine for human and veterinary medicine. They can be added to foods on both fresh and dried forms. Pudina also be effective at relieving other digestive problems such as upset stomach and indigestion.

Pinsane can be easily added to practically any dish. Pinsane has own distinct flavor, that are used in cooking and for medicinal purposes. It can improve blood flow through the body by relaxing the muscles and blood vessels.

Nannan (Coriander leaves) contains antioxidants, which can delay or prevent the spoilage of food seasoned with this spices. Leaves of these herbs are used to flavor a range of dishes and are typically fried in oil until crisp to impart flavor to all types of curry preparation. These herbs have been used in traditional medicine for variety of ailments. Nannan leave can be used in many types of dishes and meals. It is still mainly used as traditional medicine for all kinds of stomach and digestive problems.

Pyinn taw thein (Curry leaves) are used as an herb in Ayurvedic medicine. This properties include much value as an anti-diabetic, antioxidant. Pyinn taw thein is a common cooking ingredient that is added to various dishes to enhance their taste and flavor. It is used for treating various health

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problems like weight gain, blood pressure, indigestion, anemia etc. These are also known to be good for hair.

Material and Method

In this paper, four kinds of medicinal plants (Pudina, Pinsane, Nannan, Pyinn taw thein) were investigated of their elemental concentrations by AAS. Firstly, these four samples were collected from local market in Bago town ship. And washed with fresh water. For fifteen days, these leave were dried in shade at room temperature. The dried leave were crushed powered and digested with HNO_3 and H_2O_2 in 2:1 strength of homogenous solution. To increase the solubility, the sample solution of heated on hot plate at $130^\circ C$ until the volume was reduced to 3ml. Then, the solution was cooled and filtered into 25mL volumetric flask with double distilled water. After this step the total concentrations of Fe, Na, Mg, Pb, Cd etc. were analyzed by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy at the University Research Centre (URC) in Yangon.

Table 1- Difference names of four samples of interested

	Local Name	English Name	Botanical Name	Used for cooking parts
S1	Pudina	Mint leaf	<i>Mentha spicata L</i>	Leaves
S2	Pinsane	Basil	<i>Ocimum basilicum L</i>	Leaves
S3	Nannan	Coriander leaf	<i>Coriandrum satiuvam.L</i>	Leaves
S4	Pyinntawthein	Curry Leave	<i>Murrya koenigii.L</i>	Leaves

Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS)

Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) is a spectroanalytical procedure for determination of concentration elements using the absorption of optical radiation (light) by free atoms in the gaseous state. AAS is based on absorption of light by free metallic ions.

AAS can be determined over 70 different elements in solution, and is used in pharmacology, biophysics toxicology research. The technique makes use of the atomic absorption spectrum of a sample in order to assess the concentration elements contained in samples of interested. Function in short, the electrons of the atoms in the atomizer can be promoted to higher orbitals (excited state) for short period of time (nanoseconds) by absorbing a defined quantity of energy (radiation of a given wavelength). This a mount of energy is specific to a particular electron transition in a particular element. In general, each wavelength corresponds to only one element and the width of an absorption line is only of a few picometers (pm) which give the technique its elemental selectivity. Using a detector, radiation flux without sample and with sample in the atomizer is measured and the ratio between the two values (the absorbance) is converted to analyze concentration or mass using the Beer Lambert law.

Atomic constituents of a sample can be analyzed by atomizer. The flames and graphite tube atomizer are most commonly used as the atomizers. The radiation source could be an element-specific line radiation source or continuum radiation source. When the radiation passed through a monochromator, separated the element specific radiation emitted by the radiation source. Finally it measured by a detector.

AAS a steady state signal is generated during the time period when the sample is aspirated. This technique typically used for determinations in the mg/L range, and may be extended down to $\mu g/L$ for some elements.

Results and Discussions

The concentrations of element contained in samples of interested by AAS were shown in following table.

Table 1- Concentration elements contained in samples of interested

Samples	Mineral content in herbs (ppm)				Heavy metal content in herbs (ppm)			
	Fe	Na	Mg	Mn	Pb	Cd	Cu	Zn
S1	280.11	151.32	302.72	81.72	0.51	0.55	9.83	19.76
S2	261.02	90.51	210.00	71.11	0.48	0.74	8.46	10.92
S3	221.51	91.56	220.51	90.50	0.81	0.90	10.41	16.99
S4	152.45	90.99	150.75	87.36	0.48	0.90	11.01	6.94

Fig 1- Pudina leaves

Fig 2- Pinsane leaves

Fig 3- Nannan leaves

Fig 4- Pyinn taw their leaves

Fig 5- Powder of Pusinan leaves

Fig 6- Powder of Pinsane

Fig 9- sample preparation

Fig 7 - Powder of Nannan

Fig 8- Powder of Pyinn TawThein

Fig 10 - Perkin-Elmer AAnalyst 800 atomic absorption instruments

Fig 11 – Comparison of elemental concentration of samples

Elemental concentration in samples of interested were shown in table. It was found that highest concentration of iron(Fe),sodium (Na),magnesium (Mg),and zinc (Zn) were found in S1 (Pudina).Other element of manganese (Mn) and copper(Cu) were highest in S3 (Nannan) and (S4) Pyin tau then. The levels of lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd) were very similar in all samples.

Minerals such as calcium, zinc, iron and potassium in Human body are very important for body function. For this samples, iron, sodium, magnesium, manganese were contained as minerals content. Most naturally usable sources of minerals are getting from foods.

Iron is the most abundant and an essential constituent for all living thing. On the other hand, at high concentration its can tissue damage and some other diseases in humans. It is also responsible for anemia and neurodegenerative conditions in human being. The WHO (World Health Organization) recommend level of iron for daily intake is 10-28mg/day.

Sodium is an essential nutrient and is needed by the human body. It is important for many body process, such as fluid balance, muscle contraction and nervous system function. The recommended limits for sodium in the diet about 3400 mg/day. Higher sodium in Diets can increase the risk of developing high blood pressure and cardiovascular disease.

Magnesium is an important mineral. It may improve bone health both directly and in directly. The body needs magnesium to maintain the health of muscles, including the heart. A

magnesium deficiency may worsen insulin resistance. WHO recommendation of daily intake of Mg is 320 mg/day.

Manganese is an essential element for humans and other animals. Its deficiency produces severe skeletal and reproductive abnormalities in mammals. High concentration of Mn cause hazardous effects on lungs and brains of humans. WHO permissible limit of daily intake of Mg is 11 mg/day.

Lead (Pb) is a non essential heavy metal. High level accumulation of Pb in body causes anemia, colic, headache, brain damage and central nervous system disorder. WHO permissible limit of daily intake is 3mg/week.

cadmium(Cd) is also a non essential heavy metal. It is extremely toxic even at low concentration. It cause learning disabilities and hyperactivity in children. WHO permissible limit of daily intake is .3mg/week.

Copper (Cu) is an essential trace element. It is necessary for many enzymes. It needed for the normal growth and development. High concentration of Cu causes respiratory tract diseases. WHO permissible limit of daily intake is 2-3mg/day.

Zinc (Zn) is a trace element that is necessary for healthy immune system. It is responsible for a number of functions in the human body. High level of Zn is neurotoxin. WHO permissible limit of daily intake is 11mg/day.

Conclusion

In this paper, four kinds of indigenous medicinal plants (Pudina, Pinsane, Nannan, Pyinntawthein) regularly used in cooking in daily curries were investigated of their elemental concentrations by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy Method. From these results, mineral and heavy metal content in the samples were found at different levels. And a few amount of toxic elements Pb and Cd were contained. But their elemental concentration can be changed depend on the soil, season and their growing surrounding. For the reasons mentioned above, it is possible that only a few amount of these plants are seemed to be used in cooking daily curries.

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